

Dithioallophanic Acids. Part-III : Interaction of Carbon Oxysulphide with 2-S-Benzyl-1,1-Dimethyl/1-Phenyl Isothiocarbamides

R. N. DRAVID and M. S. CHANDE*

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Nagpur-440 001

Manuscript received 30 March 1981, revised 7 January 1982, accepted 12 November 1982

Interaction of carbon oxysulphide with 2-S-benzyl-1,1-dimethyl isothiocarbamide in benzene has been found to afford 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide thiocyanate, S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl thiocarbamate and S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl dithiocarbamate. 2-S-Benzyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide also affords the corresponding thiocarbamate, dithiocarbamate and in addition phenyl thiocarbamide. Mechanism has been discussed in detail.

FORMATION of dithioallophanic acid as an intermediate in the reaction of carbon oxysulphide with 2-S-benzyl-1-phenyl and 2-S-benzyl-1-methyl isothiocarbamide has been reported by us earlier^{1,2}. We now report the interaction of carbon oxysulphide with a few isothiocarbamide systems e.g., 2-S-benzyl-1,1-dimethyl isothiocarbamide (I) and 2-S-benzyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide (XI).

On carrying out the reaction of 2-S-benzyl-1,1-dimethyl isothiocarbamide (I) and carbon oxysulphide in benzene medium, a yellow colour developed slowly which grew intense and after ~6 hr a crystalline solid separated out, m.p. 160°. Benzyl mercaptan and hydrogen sulphide evolved during the reaction. On elemental analysis, the compound was found to have the empirical formula C₄H₉N₃S₂. It gave intense deep red colouration with aqueous ferric chloride solution showing the presence of thiocyanic acid in it. It was insoluble in all indifferent solvents. On attempting its crystallisation from ethanol, 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide (III) formed. The ethanolic filtrate contained thiocyanic acid. Treatment of the compound with bromine in chloroform/ethanol afforded bis-(N,N-dimethyl formamidine)disulphide dihydrobromide (IIIa). The latter must have been formed by the oxidation of 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide (III).

From the above evidence the compound was identified as an adduct (IV) of thiocyanic acid with 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide (III). Although the

thioureido grouping $\begin{matrix} \text{R} \\ \diagup \\ \text{N} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{R} \end{matrix} - \text{C} - \text{N} \begin{matrix} \diagdown \\ \text{S} \\ \diagup \end{matrix}$ decreases the

basic character of III, it is sufficiently basic to form an adduct with thiocyanic acid^{3a}. The structure of the compound (IV) has been further established by its independent synthesis. (*vide exptl*).

The benzene filtrate after removing IV, on thin layer chromatography in benzene showed the presence of dibenzyl disulphide (VI), S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl thiocarbamate (VII) and S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl dithiocarbamate (VIII). Formation of these products could be explained by the sequence of changes involving intermediate formation of dithioallophanic acid (II).

*Present address : Dept. of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Madam Cama Road, Bombay-400 032.

Dimethyl cyanamide formed in route (iv) could not be isolated as it readily combined, as soon as formed, with hydrogen sulphide to give dimethyl thiocarbamide (III) which then formed the adduct IV with thiocyanic acid obtained in step (ii).

Formation of thiocarbamide from cyanamide by sulphuration is a well known reaction^{3b}.

As reported earlier^{1,2} the source of hydrogen sulphide was the hydrolysis of carbon oxysulphide gas by alkali (the latter in earlier stages is effective in removing hydrogen sulphide formed during preparation of carbon oxysulphide) and not by any other possible alternate source.

As cyanic acid formed in step (iv) did not trimerize to cyanuric acid then, probably being volatile, it escaped⁴ or combined with I affording S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl isothiocarbamide cyanate which could not be isolated.

2-S-Benzyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide (XI), on reaction with carbon oxysulphide in benzene afforded similar products viz., phenyl thiocarbamide (XII), S-benzyl-N-phenyl thiocarbamate (XIII), S-benzyl-N-phenyl dithiocarbamate (XIV) and thiocyanic acid. The adduct of thiocyanic acid with XII could not be isolated, probably due to the resonance of lone pair of electrons on nitrogen¹ with the adjacent benzene ring thus diminishing its² basicity.

Experimental

Carbon oxysulphide gas and S-benzyl-1,1-dimethyl isothiocarbamide (I) required for the experiment were prepared by known procedures^{5,6}.

1. *Interaction of I and carbon oxysulphide in benzene medium*: I (20 g) was taken up in benzene (40 ml) and the solution dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Carbon oxysulphide gas was bubbled through the above solution in cold when a yellow colour developed. After ~3 hr, a crystalline compound started separating out. Bubbling of the gas was continued overnight. The contents of the flask on filtration gave a solid (3.0 g) which was further washed with ether (benzene filtrate was preserved for further experiment *vide expt. 3*). The compound had a m.p. 160-161°. (Found: N, 25.72; S, 39.70. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ requires N, 25.76; S, 39.20%). It gave intense deep red colouration indicating the presence of thiocyanate ion in it. It readily desulphurized⁷ on heating with aqueous sodium plumbite solution, was unstable and on standing afforded another product, m.p. 160°, which gave no depression in m.m.p. with the compound obtained on crystallisation of the product obtained by the reaction of I with COS. (Found: N, 26.81; S, 30.65. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 26.93; S, 30.77%). It was identified as 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide (III) through its m.m.p., 160°, with an authentic sample prepared by the de-*t*-butylation of 1,1-dimethyl-3-*t*-butyl thiocarbamide with hydrochloric acid⁷.

The alcoholic filtrate obtained during crystallisation of I and COS gave intense deep red colouration with aqueous ferric chloride. The compound was identified as the thiocyanic acid adduct (IV) of 1,1-dimethyl thiocarbamide.

2. *Reaction of bromine with IV*: IV (2 g) was suspended in ethanol (20 ml) and to this was then added alcoholic bromine till it was in excess when a product was obtained which was filtered (2.2 g), washed with ethanol and crystallised from dil. aq. HBr, m.p. 204°. (Found: N, 15.01; S, 17.55. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Br}_2$, mol. eq. 183, requires N, 15.29; S, 17.46%; mol. eq. 183). On heating with alkali it decomposed giving elemental sulphur. It was identified as *bis*-(N,N-dimethyl formamidine)disulphide dihydrobromide (IIIA) by m.m.p. 204° with an authentic sample prepared⁸ by the oxidation of III with bromine in ethanol, m.p., m.m.p. 204° and also through their dipicrates, m.p., m.m.p. 104° with an authentic sample.

3. *Examination of the benzene filtrate from expt. 1*: Thin layer chromatography of the filtrate from expt. 1 in benzene: carbon tetrachloride (70:30) gave 5 spots on development with iodine vapour. These were identified as dibenzyl disulphide ($R_f=0.959$), S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl dithiocarbamate ($R_f=0.852$), S-benzyl-N,N-dimethyl thiocarbamate ($R_f=0.573$). The spot with $R_f=0.483$ could not be identified. The spot which did not run was due to unreacted free base (I).

Column chromatography: The products were separated by successive elution of the column with petroleum ether (40-60°), benzene and finally with methanol. Methanolic eluate on concentration in vacuum strongly smelt of benzyl mercaptan, dimethyl amine and ammonia indicating decomposition of the product.

4. *Synthesis of IV*: 1,1-Dimethyl thiocarbamide (III; 1.2 g) was taken in dry acetone and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through it when hydrochloride of III separated out. The solid was filtered and dissolved in absolute alcohol. Potassium thiocyanate (1.0 g) was added to the alcoholic mixture and after ~ 1 hr of stirring potassium chloride separated out. The filtrate on evaporation in vacuum gave IV, m.p. 161°.

5. *Interaction of 2-S-benzyl-1-phenyl isothiocarbamide (XI) with carbon oxysulphide in benzene medium*: XI (6.0 g) was dissolved in benzene (30 ml) and carbon oxysulphide gas was bubbled through it in cold for ~ 6 hr. Initially, a yellow colour developed which deepened but no solid could be isolated. The smell of benzyl mercaptan and hydrogen sulphide was perceptible. The reaction mixture gave intense deep red colouration with aqueous ferric chloride indicating the presence of thiocyanic acid. TLC of the reaction mixture in

benzene gave five spots on development with iodine vapour. The spot with $R_f=0.923$ was due to dibenzyl disulphide (VI), and with $R_f=0.784$ was due to XIV. The spot with $R_f=0.653$ was not identified and the spot with $R_f=0.538$ was due to XIII.

Column chromatography: On eluting the reaction mixture with petroleum ether, dibenzyl disulphide was found to be present in the first fraction. Further elution of the column with benzene gave XIII, XIV and an unidentified compound. Final elution with methanol-benzene mixture (10:90) and evaporation of the solvent gave phenyl thiocarbamide (XII) and unreacted free base (XI).

References

1. R. N. DRAVID and M. S. CHANDE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20B**, 497.
2. R. N. DRAVID and M. S. CHANDE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20B**, 499.
3. E. E. REID, "Organic Chemistry of Bivalent Sulphur", Chemical Publishing Co., Inc., New York, 1963, Vol. 5, (a) p. 66; (b) p. 40.
4. N. V. SIDGWICK, "The Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1966, p. 420.
5. K. GANAPATHI and A. VENKATARAMAN, *Proc. Indian Academy Sci.*, 1945, **22A**, 362.
6. M. S. CHANDE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 941.
7. G. V. NAIR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 516.
8. F. KURZER and P. M. SANDERSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4461.